

1 **ANG is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Glioblastoma is difficult to treat and patients are often provided poor prognosis (1), indicating a
7 requirement for therapeutic target identification and drug development. Differentially expressed genes
8 represent by definition among the most promising targets for the development of novel chemotherapies (2,
9 3). We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be
10 comprehensively and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data, further limiting toxicity by
11 design (4). We mined published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify
12 differentially expressed gene products in glioblastoma by performing whole transcriptome gene expression
13 profiling. We found that the gene encoding the angiogenin, ANG, was among those whose expression was
14 most different in human glioblastoma tumors when comparing total transcription between tumor and
15 normal brain tissue. ANG expression levels were significantly increased in glioblastoma tumors as
16 compared to the non-transformed brain. ANG function at the systems level was assessed by studying
17 whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed brain. ANG is a target of interest for
18 the treatment of glioblastoma, as part of a rationally designed chemotherapeutic regimen that utilizes gene
19 expression data from patient tumors and healthy non-transformed tissues to maximize efficacy and safety
20 and minimize toxicity.

21
22
23
24
25
26 Keywords: ANG, angiogenin, glioblastoma, systems biology of glioblastoma, targeted therapeutics in
27 glioblastoma.

Brain cancer encompasses a spectrum of solid tumors that affect the brain in children and adults including medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma, and glioblastoma (7). Rational development of targeted therapeutics to treat patients with glioblastoma can be supported by an enhanced understanding of fundamental transcriptional differences that define the glioblastoma tumor. To discover genes associated with glioblastoma in humans in an unbiased fashion and at the systems level, we compared total transcription in the normal brain and in the glioblastoma tumor using published and public human glioblastoma microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify a molecular signature or fingerprint of glioblastoma, among the most lethal and difficult to treat solid tumors affecting adults. We describe here identification of a potential therapeutic target in glioblastoma based on quantitative whole transcriptome methods.

Methods

We utilized microarray datasets GSE116520 (5) and GSE184643 (6) for this differential gene expression analysis of the brain cancer glioblastoma in humans using R-based computational methods (GEO2R). GSE116520 was generated using Illumina HumanHT-12 V4.0 expression beadchip technology; for this analysis, we used $n=8$ control brain tissue and $n=17$ glioblastoma tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL10558. GSE184643 was generated using Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Homo sapiens) technology; for this analysis, we used $n=3$ control brain tissue and $n=3$ glioblastoma tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL24676. All tumors utilized for differential gene expression analysis here were of the adenocarcinoma type. The Benjamini and Hochberg method of p-value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p-values were used to assess statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used. SEEK was utilized for transcriptional co-regulation studies (8).

Results

We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technologies and cross-laboratory validation (5, 6) to discover in an unbiased fashion and at the transcriptome level the most distinguishing gene expression features of the human brain cancer glioblastoma.

ANG is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.

1. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with glioblastoma

$n=8$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=17$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1760727	1.97E-04	-4.0842731	0.193376	-1.31568297	ANG	7629/47229	83.8

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma tumor tissue, we discovered differential expression of angiogenin, encoded by ANG in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of ANG changed more than 80% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 47,229 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of

1 ANG messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of ANG during
 2 transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

3
 4 2. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with brain cancer: glioblastoma.

5 $n=3$ normal brain tissues (human)

6 $n=3$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

7

ID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	Gene	Rank	%DE
283	2.42E-03	0.56	-3.0330833	-1.6978659	ANG	2729/19678	86.1

8

9 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
 10 tumors in a second RNA-sequencing dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort,
 11 we validated differential expression of ANG in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of
 12 ANG here changed more than 85% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering
 13 all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,678 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the
 14 negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of ANG messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors,
 15 demonstrating up-regulation of ANG during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to
 16 glioblastoma.

17 Thus, ANG is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the
 18 glioblastoma subtype in humans.

19 ANG transcriptional co-regulation.

20 Finally, we utilized a separate systems methodology that utilizes whole transcriptome data to
 21 provide insight into molecular function of a gene product by evaluating the transcriptional network within
 22 which it operates through identification of co-regulated gene partners.

27 In the transformed brain, ANG was transcriptionally co-regulated with CD44, CD109, and
 28 ANXA1.

1 Thus, blind comparative transcriptome analysis of glioblastomas revealed differential expression of
2 ANG as among the most significant transcriptional features of glioblastoma tumors; systems level query
3 into ANG molecular function across multiple tissues at the transcriptome level revealed its co-regulation
4 with CD44, CD109, and ANXA1.

4 **Discussion**

5 We found by mining published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) that the
6 angiogenin, ANG, was among the genes most differentially expressed in the primary tumors of patients
7 with glioblastoma; ANG was expressed at significantly higher levels in glioblastoma tumors as compared
8 to the brain. ANG is a target of interest for rationally designed medical treatment of glioblastoma, a
9 difficult to treat adult solid tumor.
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Alexander, B.M. and Cloughesy, T.F., 2017. Adult glioblastoma. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 35(21), pp.2402-2409.
2. Liu, A.Y., 2000. Differential expression of cell surface molecules in prostate cancer cells. *Cancer research*, 60(13), pp.3429-3434.
3. Singer, S., Socci, N.D., Ambrosini, G., Sambol, E., Decarolis, P., Wu, Y., O'Connor, R., Maki, R., Viale, A., Sander, C. and Schwartz, G.K., 2007. Gene expression profiling of liposarcoma identifies distinct biological types/subtypes and potential therapeutic targets in well-differentiated and dedifferentiated liposarcoma. *Cancer research*, 67(14), pp.6626-6636.
4. Muller, P.Y. and Milton, M.N., 2012. The determination and interpretation of the therapeutic index in drug development. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 11(10), pp.751-761.
5. Kruthika, B.S., Jain, R., Arivazhagan, A., Bharath, R.D., Yasha, T.C., Kondaiah, P. and Santosh, V., 2019. Transcriptome profiling reveals PDZ binding kinase as a novel biomarker in peritumoral brain zone of glioblastoma. *Journal of neuro-oncology*, 141, pp.315-325.
6. GSE184643. Xiong Jin. Henan University, School of Pharmacy. Henan Key Laboratory of Brain Targeted Bio-nanomedicine. China.
7. Omuro, A. and DeAngelis, L.M., 2013. Glioblastoma and other malignant gliomas: a clinical review. *Jama*, 310(17), pp.1842-1850.
8. Zhu, Q., Wong, A.K., Krishnan, A., Aure, M.R., Tadych, A., Zhang, R., Corney, D.C., Greene, C.S., Bongo, L.A., Kristensen, V.N. and Charikar, M., 2015. Targeted exploration and analysis of large cross-platform human transcriptomic compendia. *Nature methods*, 12(3), pp.211-214.